

HOW MUCH EXERCISE IS TOO MUCH EXERCISE: A LOOK AT EXERCISE
ADDICTION IN COLLEGE STUDENTS

by

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Abstract

Exercise is essential for physical, mental, and emotional health; however, there is a significant distinction between healthy and unhealthy exercise habits. While the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) suggests approximately 150 minutes of physical activity per week, individuals who engage in more time than that may develop obsessional exercise habits. Some individuals develop exercise addiction, which is described as compulsive exercise characterized by intrinsic or obligatory motivation, psychological dependence, increased physiological tolerance, and prioritizing exercise over life. Compulsive exercise can result in the development of other mental health issues such as muscle and body dysmorphia, depression, anxiety, and obsessive-compulsive disorder (Vieria, 2021). My project focuses specifically on the manifestation of exercise addiction in male and female college students, and how it affects body and muscle dysmorphia, self-esteem, and body image. Undergraduate students from California State University, Fullerton completed a survey about their exercise habits, self-esteem, body image, and body and muscle dysmorphia. The goal is to test if there is a correlation between exercise habits and mental health regarding body image, and identify any potential gender differences. Using chi-square tests of independence, data were analyzed to address the potential differences between male and female college students' perceptions of body image, self-esteem, body dysmorphia, and muscle dysmorphia. The purpose of this study is to bring awareness about unhealthy exercise habits and prospective risks for such behaviors.

How Much Exercise is Too Much Exercise: A Look at Exercise Addiction in College Students

Introduction

Defining Exercise Addiction

In the United States, approximately 53.3 percent of adults aged 18 and older report exercising regularly (CDC, 2021). While exercise is vital for improving physical, mental, and emotional health, there is a fine line between healthy and unhealthy exercise habits. Some individuals may develop an obsession with exercise and fitness, also known as exercise addiction. Exercise addiction is described as compulsive exercise characterized by intrinsic or obligatory motivation, psychological dependence, increased physiological tolerance, and prioritizing exercise over life. For some, exercise addiction is similar to that of behavioral addiction with symptoms of uncontrollable behaviors, withdrawal, increased exercise time, continuance, and a reduction in other activities (Freimuth et al., 2011). Such compulsive and addictive behaviors can cause individuals to neglect their physical health, social life, and mental wellbeing.

Compulsive exercise can result in the development of other mental health conditions such as muscle dysmorphia, body dysmorphic disorder, depression, anxiety, and obsessive-compulsive disorder (Vieria, 2021). Understanding the significance of compulsive exercise and the possible effects it can have on a person's physical and mental health is essential for researchers studying this area. The purpose of the current study is to examine and compare how exercise addiction manifests in male and female college students, and how it relates to body and muscle dysmorphia, self-esteem, and body image.

History of Exercise Addiction

As early as the 1970s, William Glasser reported an addiction to running and suggested that runners develop a positive addiction to compulsive exercise as a result of positive psychological effects, such as joy and pleasure, or runner's high (Lichtenstein et al., 2017). A high volume of research regarding the consequences of exercise dependence was conducted during the 1970s, but very little modern research regarding the underlying trends of exercise addiction has been analyzed (Parastatidou et al., 2014). Existing research on compulsive exercise has implemented the Exercise Addiction Inventory which looks at addiction in six different areas of psychological and physical experience, including salience, conflict, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, and relapse (Griffiths et al., 2005). Correlated symptoms of compulsive exercise are often associated with body dissatisfaction, low self-esteem and self-image, anxiety about health, rigidity, perfectionism, and compulsiveness (Hall et al., 2009). Individuals with exercise addiction typically display a high need for achievement, muscular physique, perceived exercise competence, self-esteem, and obsessive passion (Gonzalez-Cutre & Sicilia 2012).

Theories and Evidence

The DSM-5 classifies excessive exercise under "behavioral addiction," in which behavior becomes obsessive, compulsive, and causes dysfunction in a person's life (Potenza, 2014). While working out often supports features of positive mental health, the link between exercise and maladaptive behaviors is complex and, at present, poorly understood (Scharmer et al., 2020). Most researchers consider maladaptive exercise habits to be related to eating disorder pathology and impairments. Additionally, excessive exercise clusters with traits associated with increased psychopathology including obsessive-compulsive behaviors, anxiety, perfectionism, body image dissatisfaction, reward dependence, and anhedonia (Scharmer et al., 2020).

Compulsive exercise and exercise dependence are the main areas of focus for researchers studying maladaptive exercise practices. Individuals who have compulsions to exercise may develop dependence on exercise which can change the psychological and physiological effects of exercise, over time. If an individual with exercise dependence misses a workout, they are more likely to experience feelings of guilt or anxiety (Scharmer et al., 2020). Exercise dependence is also characterized by tolerance to exercise benefits, such that an individual may no longer derive mood enhancement through exercise (Scharmer et al., 2020). Exercise is considered compulsive when an individual exercises because they feel obligated to exercise (Scharmer et al., 2020). These obligatory feelings can be identified as a variable that increases exercise compulsions to maintain a specific physique or body image. A large proportion of the existing research about compulsive exercise has analyzed the psychological impact that exercise dependence can have on eating habits and disorders (Bardone-Cone et al., 2016; Blaydon & Lindner, 2002; Trott et al., 2020).

Research suggests that the degree of distress associated with changes in physical activity routine is more informative than the quantity of exercise, when predicting eating disorder-related pathology (Bardone-Cone et al., 2016). Similar to eating disorders, compulsive exercise habits can function to avoid anxiety related to the negative outcomes of not exercising, such as weight gain and body changes (Dittmer et al., 2018). Additionally, such behaviors can be maintained through positive reinforcement of exercising (e.g., weight loss, muscle toning, mood improvement). A large proportion of the research about exercise addiction in relation to eating disorders, and there is minimal research that focuses on exercise addiction alone.

Shortcomings of Current Research

Women's engagement in exercise has been studied less extensively than men's. In the past, women often reported more barriers to exercise and less control over their decision to exercise due to more gender role responsibilities, such as childcare and housework (Stephens & Craig, 1990). Previous analyses have attributed the limited female presence in the weight room to the predominantly masculine environment and culture of the gym (Craig & Liberti, 2007). Existing research about physical activity interventions targeting specific populations do not focus solely on women or the gender-specific barriers to physical exercise they experience (Segar et al., 2008). Additional research analyzing more modern trends about the types of exercise females engage in should be conducted to determine if there have been any changes over the last decade.

In addition to the types of exercise engaged in, there is minimal research regarding the differences between males and females in exercise addiction. Since compulsive exercise was first identified and studied in the 1970s, there has been a dramatic shift and change in the way that men and women exercise. Historically, gyms have been identified as more masculine spaces, and more programs were targeted to individuals based on their gender (Bladh, 2022). In the past, women worked out to maintain a slender physique, and they would often focus on more cardio and dance-based exercise (Bladh, 2022; Segar et al., 2008; Marcus & Forsyth, 1998; Scharff et al., 1999; Lutter, 1994; Verhoef et al., 1992). However, there has been a shift for women to engage in more weight training in the last few decades (Heap, 2021; Fernandez et al., 2020, Norris, 2019, Thibault et al., 2010). Researchers previously have identified that at any given time there may be a 90/10-percent or 80/20-percent gender split in the gym (Dworkin, 2003). In the last decade, there has been a growing presence of women in the weight room (Norris, 2019; Craig & Liberti, 2007; Johansson, 1996). Many women who exercise cite it as being a source of

power and agency which rejects the narrow constructions of femininity and allows for physical and emotional strength (Dworkin, 2003).

An abundance of research regarding males' involvement in the weight room and exercise has been conducted (Norris, 2019; Lavalley & Mansfield, 2013; Thibault et al., 2010; Johansson, 1996); however, there is less emphasis on the potentially harmful effects of fitness on men's mental health. Male participation in sports and physical fitness has historically perpetuated conceptions of masculinity and heterosexuality (Dworkin, 2003). The perception that manhood is determined by muscularity and physical strength can lead to body image issues and muscle dysmorphia, such that men feel their bodies are inadequate if they are "too small" or "not big enough."

The present study will analyze exercise addiction, the types of exercise engaged in, and the amount of time spent exercising in relation to gender identity, to address gaps in the existing literature.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Females will spend less time exercising than males.

Hypothesis 2: Men will be more likely to engage in weight lifting workouts, while women will be more likely to engage in cardio and aerobic exercise.

Hypothesis 3: Exercise addiction will be significantly different between males and females, such that male college students will score higher on the Exercise Addiction Inventory than female college students.

Method

Participants

A total of 53 adults ranging between the ages of 18 and 30 participated in the study; however, only 48 adults completed the survey in its entirety (M age= 21, SD = 1.89). The participants were predominantly college undergraduate students consisting of 10 male-identifying students, 25 female-identifying students, and 13 students who declined to state their gender identity. Of the 48 participants, approximately 5.4% were Native American, 2.7% were African American, 5.4% were Asian American, 73.0% were White, and 13.5% were two or more races. Approximately 27.0% of the participants (n = 10) identified with the Hispanic, Latinx, or Spanish ethnicity, and the remaining 73% (n = 38) identified with the non Hispanic, Latinx, or Spanish ethnicity.

Measures

Body Image Scale

The Body Image Scale (BIS) is a patient-reported outcome measure intended to evaluate body image (Hopwood et al., 2001). The BIS is a 10-item scale addressing topics ranging from general body image to feelings of attractiveness (Hopwood et al., 2001). Items are scored on a four-point scale (0 “not at all” to 3 “very much”). The total score ranges between 0 and 30; higher scores indicate a greater level of body image dissatisfaction (Hopwood et al., 2001). The scale showed high reliability (Cronbach’s alpha 0.93) and clinical validity based on response prevalence, discriminant validity (p <0.0001), sensitivity to change (p <0.0001), and consistency of scores (Hopwood et al., 2001).

Body Dysmorphic Disorder Questionnaire (BDDQ)

The Body Dysmorphic Disorder Questionnaire (BDDQ) is a brief self-report screening measure for body dysmorphic disorder. Body dysmorphia is characterized by distressing and impairing preoccupation with perceived defects in appearance (Brohede et al., 2013). The questionnaire asks four yes/no questions about concerns with physical appearance, and each question has sub questions that ask for more elaboration about responses to yes/no questions (Phillips, 2002). If respondents answer 'yes' to a majority of the questions, they are identified as being at risk for having body dysmorphic disorder, however, additional psychological evaluation needs to be conducted (Brohede et al., 2013). The screening tool implements items about preoccupation with appearance, distress, interference with functioning, and avoidance relating to appearance (Phillips, 2002). The open-ended questions allow for elaboration and discussion about feelings of body dysmorphia.

Drive for Muscularity Scale (DMS)

The Drive for Muscularity Scale (DMS) is a 15-item self-report questionnaire evaluating attitudes and behaviors associated with the desire for a more muscular physique (McCreary & Sasse, 2000). Participants are asked to respond to items rated on a six-point response scale (1= *Never* to 6= *Always*), with higher scoring totals indicating higher levels of drive for muscularity. The DMS includes items about body composition, such as "I wish I were more muscular," "I think I would feel more confident if I had more muscle mass," and "I think my arms are not muscular enough." The validity of the scale was identified through research regarding the degree to which the DMS is associated with theoretical constructs uncorrelated with ratings on a muscular-based figure silhouette scale (McCreary & Sasse, 2000). The DMS has an alpha reliability ranging from 0.85 to 0.91 for male participants, and 0.80 for female participants (McCreary & Sasse, 2000).

Exercise Addiction Inventory (EAI)

The Exercise Addiction Inventory (EAI) is a psychometric instrument developed to identify individuals who are affected by, or at risk of exercise addiction (Griffiths et al., 2005). The EAI is a six item scale that explores the psychometric properties of addiction to exercise. The items on the survey include: (1) Exercise is the most important thing in my life, (2) Conflicts have arisen between me and my family and/ or my partner about the amount of exercise I do, (3) I use exercise as a way of changing my mood, (4) Over time I have increased the amount of exercise I do in a day, (5) If I have to miss an exercise session I feel moody and irritable, (6) If I cut down the amount of exercise I do, and then start again, I always end up exercising as often as I did before. Items were scored on a five-point scale (1= *Strongly disagree* to 5= *Strongly agree*). Higher scores indicate higher levels of exercise addiction. Preliminary and test-retest reliability of the scale are considered very good (0.85). Research about the concurrent validity found significant correlation with the EAI (Griffiths et al., 2005).

Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale (RSE)

The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSE) is a 10-point scale developed to measure the self-esteem of high schoolers; however, it has since been generalized to a variety of groups (Rosenberg, 1979). The 10 points of the RSE are as follows: (1) On the whole, I am satisfied with myself, (2) At times I think I am no good at all, (3) I feel that I have a number of good qualities, (4) I am able to do things as well as most other people, (5) I feel I do not have much to be proud of, (6) I certainly feel useless at times, (7) I feel that I'm a person of worth, (8) I wish I could have more respect for myself, (9) All in all, I am inclined to think that I am a failure, and (10) I take a positive attitude toward myself. Participants select one of four responses— 1= Strongly agree, 2= Agree, 3= Disagree, or 4= Strongly disagree— to each individual item. The

reliability of the Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale has good predictive reliability, as the Cronbach coefficient is high ($M= 0.81$).

The RSE is a Guttman scale, which scores using combined ratings. Low self-esteem responses are “disagree” or “strongly disagree” on items 1, 3, 4, 7, 10, and “strongly agree” or “agree” on items 2, 5, 6, 8, 9 (Rosenberg, 1979). Two or three out of three correct responses to items 3, 7, and 9 are scored as one item (Rosenberg, 1979). One or two out of two correct responses for items 4 and 5 are identified as single items (Rosenberg, 1979). Items 1, 8, and 10 are scored as individual items (Rosenberg, 1979). Combined correct responses for items 2 and 6 are considered single items (Rosenberg, 1979). The scale can also be scored by totalling the individual 4-point items after reverse-scoring the negatively worded items (Rosenberg, 1979). For the purpose of this study, the latter option is implemented.

Procedure

Participants were recruited through the CSUF psychology research pool and asked to complete a Qualtrics survey. Students who elected to participate in the study used the SONA system platform to take the survey for course credit.

Results

In order to test hypothesis 1, a chi-square test of independence was conducted to examine whether there was a pattern of relationship between gender and amount of time spent in minutes exercising per day. The results demonstrate no significant pattern of relationship between minutes spent exercising per day and gender, $\chi^2(10)= 13.953, p= 0.175$.

A chi-square test of independence was performed to determine whether there was a pattern of relationship between gender and number of days per week spent exercising. The results demonstrate no significant pattern of relationship between days spent exercising and

gender, $\chi^2(6)= 9.541, p= 0.145$.

A chi-square test of independence was conducted to examine whether the relation between gender and type of exercise was significant. The results demonstrate no significant pattern of relationship between gender and type of exercise, $\chi^2(10)= 3.857, p= 0.954$.

A chi-square goodness of fit test was conducted to analyze the relationship between responses to questions on the Exercise Addiction Inventory in relation to gender identity. The results demonstrate no significant pattern of relationship based on gender identity in relation to individual responses to EAI item 1, $\chi^2(8)= 9.890, p= 0.273$. The results demonstrate no significant pattern of relationship based on gender identity in relation to individual responses to EAI item 2, $\chi^2(8)= 10.738, p= 0.217$. No significant pattern of relationship was demonstrated based on gender identity in relation to individual responses to EAI item 3, $\chi^2(8)= 11.372, p= 0.182$. For EAI item 4 and gender identity, no significant pattern of relationship was found, such that $\chi^2(8)= 5.384, p= 0.716$. No significant pattern of relationship was demonstrated based on gender identity in relation to individual responses to EAI item 5, $\chi^2(8)= 14.338, p= 0.073$. The results demonstrate no significant pattern of relationship based on gender identity in relation to individual responses to EAI item 6, $\chi^2(8)= 4.353, p= 0.824$.

Discussion

In the present study, we aimed to provide analyses for potential patterns of relationship between gender identity and exercise-related variables. The results of this study offer several new insights. Specifically, the study found that gender identity did not have a pattern of relationship for exercise addiction, type of exercise engaged in, and amount of time spent exercising. The results of this study refuted the hypotheses that there would be significant

patterns of relationship between gender identity for college students and the exercise variables identified in the study.

Previous studies identified male college students as more physically active than their female counterparts, such that males engage in more time exercising than females (Armstrong et al., 2018). However, there are no studies that look at gender beyond a binary and include gender identification on a spectrum. The present study allowed participants to identify their gender as man, woman, trans man, trans woman, gender nonbinary, fluid, other, and decline to state. This study concludes that there is no significant pattern of relationship between amount of time spent exercising and gender identity; thus proposing that there are no gender differences between the number of days per week and hours per day that college students exercise. Approximately, 52.1 percent of participants identified themselves as women, 20.8 percent identified as men, and 27.1 declined to state their gender identity. The findings of this research provide results regarding the amount of time college students exercise with a more holistic approach to gender identification, and identify no patterns of relation. In this regard, the gap between how much time college students exercise relating to gender identification is starting to close. This change may be the result of the evolving conversations and perspectives about how we identify gender. The implications of this research may generate future research that looks at gender and time spent exercising in more depth.

Statistical analyses were conducted to provide additional research regarding gender and the type of exercise performed. Previous research identifies males as more likely to engage in strength and weight-based exercises, such as weight lifting, and females as more likely to engage in cardio or aerobic exercises (Achon, 2022). The current study hypothesized that more males would lift weights for exercise than females; however, there was no pattern of relationship

identified between gender and type of exercise engaged in. Potential implications of these results may include the changing societal expectations of female body composition (i.e., more muscular than slender). Additionally, the growing media presence of females in the weightroom may also help explain why there is no pattern of relationship between gender and type of exercise.

Similarly, a handful of the participants who declined to state their gender also responded that they lift weights. The implications of this can help illustrate how people of different genders may choose to exercise and what the changing gym environment may look like. The results of this study contribute more information about this evolving relationship. One study noted similar trends between female gym goers and the type of exercise they engage in, and they attributed it to societal expectations of female body composition that has led to an increase of females in the weightroom (Dworkin, 2003).

Prior research has indicated that males demonstrate greater exercise addiction than females; thus it was hypothesized men would score higher on the EAI than women or other respondents. The findings of this study did not support the hypothesis, such that there were no significant patterns of relationship between gender and exercise addiction. These results provide updated information about the changing demographics of gym goers and routine exercisers. In the past, college-age men were two times as likely to exercise excessively and were more prone to irritability and anxiety if they missed a workout, than their female counterparts (Hausenblas & Symons Downs, 2002). The results of the present study suggest there is a potential change in the prevalence of exercise addiction for women and individuals who chose not to identify their gender. Understanding the patterns of exercise addiction and how trends may be changing, is essential for educating and assisting college students who may engage in compulsive exercising.

For the purpose of this study, participants were asked to identify their gender on a non-binary spectrum to allow for a more socially relevant understanding of gender identity and exercise. Research looking at gender differences and exercise-related variables has not analyzed gender as a fluid, non-binary variable. As the discussion about gender identity and gender differences continues to evolve, research analyzing gender differences should also change. For each of the exercise-related variables analyzed in this study, no significant patterns of relationship with gender were identified. The implications of these findings may suggest that the way we define gender and gender-related social expectations, such as body composition and body image, have shifted over time to allow for more inclusivity of people of all genders in exercise. The aspects of gender identity and sexuality have undergone much social change that have expanded mainstream perceptions. With the shift away from binaries, there is a better understanding of gender on a spectrum and more individuals feel comfortable identifying with a nonbinary gender. Given the results of this study, gender may not be a relevant variable to analyze in relation to the type of exercise engaged in, time spent exercising, and exercise addiction. As gender roles and expectations change, the variable of gender identity may not be as salient when conducting research. Future research on this topic should analyze a different variable of interest, such as age, to determine if there are any other patterns of relationship.

Limitations and Future Directions

Among this study's limitations were its self-selection bias. Given the title and content of the research study, respondents who do not exercise may not participate in the study. Similarly, the sensitive content of the study (i.e., body image, self-esteem, body dysmorphia, muscle dysmorphia, gender identity) may prevent participants from wanting to participate in the study. Additional research with a larger and more diverse sample may provide different results; a

majority of the participants were identified as White (73.0%) and females (52.1%). To gather a more representative study, a larger body of students should be collected to reduce response bias.

Future Directions

Additional research that includes participants who exercise and those who do not, could provide a more representative sample. Given the potential self-selection bias, a broad sample of people who engage in varying physical activities. To provide better insight about gender identity and the way college students perceive their bodies, more information about further research and analyses regarding body composition, exercise habits, and body dysmorphia for college students should be conducted. The findings of this research could demonstrate the habits and psychological responses to the traits that characterize body dysmorphic disorder.

Conclusion

Exercise addiction is a psychological and physiological condition that affects approximately three-percent of the United States population (CDC, n.d.); however our understanding of exercise addiction relating to gender identity has received little attention by researchers. Analyzing exercise variables, including amount of time spent exercising, type of exercise engaged in, and responses to the Exercise Addiction Inventory, and gender identity for potential patterns of relationship can address gaps in the literature and updated information about exercise habits for college students. Since no patterns of relationship were identified for the exercise-related variables and gender identity, it provides research a better understanding of how the changing discussion of gender identity plays a role in the development of exercise addiction, how long individuals exercise, and type of exercise engaged in. Given the findings of this research, more advocacy highlighting the potential risks of exercise habits for individuals of all gender identities should be encouraged and considered.

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